

AI & Government (AIG) – Interim Report (Phase 1)

University of Edinburgh Major Initiatives Fund 2025–26

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1. Executive Summary

This interim report maps completed and ongoing research, teaching and executive education activities related to Artificial Intelligence (AI) in government and the public sector (excluding the Health and Education systems) across the University of Edinburgh. We have identified 70 research initiatives involving 72 researchers, and 34 relevant courses and degrees (both undergraduate and postgraduate), and 4 exec-ed programmes, indicating a substantial and diverse presence in this field across the University. The list is indicative rather than exhaustive and will be refined as further activity is identified through consultation and outreach.

Key Findings

- The strongest area of activity is the Governance of AI, reflecting both past and ongoing research in regulation, assurance, ethical oversight, transparency, and public trust, anchored across EFI, SPS, PPLS and Law, and extending into national and international policy discussions. This is followed by substantial work on AI in Policymaking.
- Both Governance of AI and AI in Policymaking function as cross-cutting areas of strength, appearing across multiple policy domains and levels of government. This indicates that the University’s expertise is not isolated within specific sectors, but forms a cross-cutting capability.
- Across policy domains, the strongest concentrations lie in Policing, Border Control, Internal Security and Migration; Justice and the Legal System; Climate, Energy and the Environment; and Welfare and Social Services. There is also notable activity in Media and Public Information. By contrast, there is comparatively less work in Economic and Financial Governance, Foreign and Development Policy, Military and Defence, and Emergency Services.

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- Engagement spans multiple levels of government. The strongest concentration is with UK central government and executive agencies, followed by international organisations and Scottish government and other devolved governments, with additional collaboration at local authority and frontline service levels.
- Teaching provision is strongest at postgraduate level, particularly within EFI and the SPS.
- Cross-School executive education in AI is already emerging as an institutional strength, with open and tailored programmes delivered across the Business School, Informatics, EFI and Law. This provides a strong base for expanding professional training aligned with public-sector needs.
- Three cross-cutting priorities for the next phase of the initiative emerged: strengthening internal visibility and collaborative capacity across Schools; improving the University's ability to mobilise external funding through research, consultancy, and executive education; and positioning Edinburgh as a leading centre of expertise and a first point of contact for government partners on AI in the public sector.

2. Introduction

This report provides an overview of research, teaching and executive education (exec-ed) activities across the University of Edinburgh (UoE) that engage with artificial intelligence (AI) in government and public-sector contexts. The mapping covers AI use across public-policy domains but excludes the Health and Education sectors, as both are major areas of study in their own right, and already the focus of dedicated institutional initiatives (including the AI and Health Programme funded by the Major Initiatives Fund and the Centre for Research in Digital Education). Examining these domains would require separate, focused mapping exercises. Both themes, however, are considered in scope where work concerns health and education *government policy* (as opposed to broader aspects of service organisation and delivery).

The aim of the work presented in this report is to establish a clearer sense of the landscape: where current activities are concentrated, where similar questions are being approached from different directions, and where there may be scope for collaboration or joint development of new activities. The findings are based on desk-based mapping conducted in the first phase of the project, drawing on project websites, PURE profiles, funding records, and published outputs. Both completed and ongoing research activities were included. This is an initial view rather than a definitive audit; the dataset will be refined and expanded in the next stage through direct consultation with researchers to ensure accuracy and to capture work that may not yet be publicly visible.

The current mapping covers research, teaching and executive education activities. We developed a framework that distinguishes four types of AI use in public-sector settings (administration and organisational processes; policymaking; participatory and consultative processes; and governance of AI) and classifies engagement by level of government and policy domain. Using this framework, we

summarise the distribution of AI & Government activity across the University and provide examples from different Schools and research units to illustrate areas of concentration. The framework serves as a starting point for categorising existing work, and is not meant to accurately reflect disciplinary or sectoral boundaries accurately.

The structure of the report is as follows. Section 3 outlines research activity using the shared typology. Section 4 summarises teaching provision. Section 5 summarises exec-ed provision. Section 6 discusses implications and next steps. Section 7 sets out the emerging priorities that arose from the workshop convened on 24 November 2025. Section 8 presents the methodology applied in producing this report.

3. Overview of Existing AI & Government Research Activities within UoE

3.1 How is AI Used for Public Policy Research in UoE?

The mapping identified four main ways in which AI is being used or studied across the University in relation to research around government and public policy. Together, these account for more than sixty projects, hubs, and initiatives. While presented as distinct categories, many projects span multiple dimensions. The examples listed below are illustrative rather than exhaustive and highlight the breadth of activity across different Schools and Centres.

Governance of AI

We identified at least 41 research activities from 22 researchers focusing on how AI systems are regulated, assessed and made accountable within public-sector contexts, including existing and proposed frameworks that ensure transparency, ethical standards, and public trust. This area represents one of the University's strongest and most visible contributions to national and international policy discussions on responsible AI. It brings together expertise across Law, Informatics, Philosophy, Psychology and Language Sciences (PPLS), Edinburgh Futures Institute (EFI) and Social and Political Science (SPS), connecting normative and technical work through partnerships with regulators, government agencies, and industry. Flagship examples include [*Bridging Responsible AI Divides \(BRAID\)*](#), [*Neuropolitics Research Lab*](#)'s work on ethical and accountable AI, the [*Centre for Research into Information, Surveillance and Privacy \(CRISP\)*](#), and the [*Trustworthy Autonomous Systems Node in Governance and Regulation*](#).

AI in Policymaking

At least 34 research activities conducted by 23 researchers have focused on applying AI to inform, design, or evaluate public policy. These projects use computational methods, natural language processing, and

predictive modelling to enhance the evidence base for decision-making across domains including health, digital communication, and environmental governance. Examples include the cross-school collaboration [*Can Topic Modelling of Local Newspaper Texts Enhance Understanding of Neighbourhood Effects on Health?*](#), which captures local social factors influencing health resilience and spatial inequalities; the [*Good Governance and Rule of Law*](#) project, which develops a values-based framework to guide data-driven public health policy during emergencies; the [*SMASH \(Social Media Analysis and Support for Humanity\) Research Group*](#), which applies AI and language models to study misinformation, online harms, and digital behaviour in support of emerging regulatory and communication policies; the [*AI for Digital Twin Earth \(AI4DTE\)*](#) collaboration with the European Space Agency, which integrates AI-driven simulation and forecasting tools to support environmental policy planning and impact assessment; and [*PeaceRep's PeaceTech*](#) programme, which applies AI-based text analysis and translation to enhance the accessibility and analysis of peace agreements and to support international mediation and conflict-resolution policy.

AI in Administration and Organisational Processes

At least 27 research activities from 23 researchers apply AI to improve the internal operations, data infrastructure, and technical workflows of public bodies and partner institutions. The emphasis is on optimisation of service delivery, document and knowledge pipelines, secure data integration, and compute efficiency—capabilities that underpin evidence use across government. Examples include [*Scottish Centre for Administrative Data Research \(SCADR\)*](#), which uses machine-learning-based record linkage to reconstruct life courses and build a trusted national administrative data infrastructure, and the [*AI for Net Zero*](#) project in collaboration with EPCC, which applies machine learning and digital twin approaches for operational planning and optimisation in critical infrastructure such as energy and transport.

AI in Participatory and Consultative Processes

A smaller cluster of work is concerned with using AI to support public deliberation, consultation, and practitioner participation in decision-making. We identified at least 14 activities in this area, involving 11 researchers. The focus is on using AI not only as a technical tool but as a means to support inclusion, accountability, and shared input into how technologies and policies are designed and implemented.

Examples include [*Making AI Intelligible for Public Service Journalism*](#), which works with the BBC to co-design value-aligned newsroom practices and strengthen journalists' understanding of algorithmic systems; [*Data and Design for Property Planning*](#) project conducted with Edinburgh Living Lab and City of Edinburgh Council, which integrates AI-informed data analysis with community engagement to support place-based planning; and [*Fixing the Future*](#), which explores reparability and digital equity through participatory design of more sustainable and accessible Internet-of-Things technologies.

3.2 How Does UoE Research Engage Government and Public-Sector Contexts?

The University's AI & Government research activities span multiple layers of governance, from international organisations to frontline service delivery. For analytical clarity, projects are classified along two dimensions: Levels of Government (L1–L5), capturing the locus of authority, and Policy Areas (PA1–PA10), reflecting the substantive domains of public policy (see Section 7.1.2 for typology). Many initiatives sit at the intersection of multiple categories. For example, the [*AI for Digital Twin Earth*](#) collaboration operates across international governance *and* climate and environmental policy, while the [*SCRIPT Centre*](#) engages with regulation and oversight, justice and legal systems, *and* policing and security through its focus on AI law and ethics. Therefore, these categories should be understood as overlapping rather than discrete.

3.2.1 Levels of Government

The most extensive engagement is with **UK central government and executive agencies** (L2), where we identified at least 28 research activities. Much of this work examines how AI is adopted, governed, and operationalised within national public institutions. For example, [*Intelligible AI for Resilience in Public Service Journalism*](#) project convenes AI researchers, ethicists and journalists to examine how algorithmic systems shape editorial judgement and newsroom workflows in UK public broadcasting. The [*Smart Data Foundry*](#) provides secure, privacy-protected access to large-scale financial datasets to inform economic policy, resilience and social wellbeing, while the [*Making Systems Answer Responsibility Project*](#) contributes to national guidance on assurance, accountability and governance mechanisms for AI used in public-sector decision environments.

We also identified 22 projects engaging **International and Transnational bodies** (L1). For example, the [*Childlight Global Child Safety Institute*](#) works across international organisations, governments and civil society groups to improve the collection, analysis and governance of data related to child safety, risk and online harm. The [*Carrots & Sticks*](#) project, originally launched by the United Nations Environment Programme and developed in partnership with the Global Reporting Initiative, supports the standardisation and evaluation of environmental, social, and governance policies across jurisdictions. Similarly, [*PeaceRep's PeaceTech*](#) programme—collaborating with the United Nations, World Bank, and regional organisations such as the African Union—develops AI tools that enhance cross-language analysis and accessibility of peace agreements, supporting international mediation and peacebuilding efforts.

A further 18 projects collaborate with **Scottish Government and other devolved governments** (L3), including [*Chamberfakes*](#), which examines the risks posed by generative AI to parliamentary democracy in Scotland; ongoing work in the [*Neuropolitics Research Lab*](#), which supports Scottish Government and parliamentary actors through data-informed research on digital influence, democratic resilience, and policy engagement; and the [*Edinburgh Earth Initiative*](#), which contributes to the Scotland's Beyond Net Zero agenda through AI-driven climate modelling and sustainability research.

In addition, 14 projects support **local and regional authorities** (L4), focusing on how AI supports local service delivery and participatory urban governance. For example, [*Data and Design for Property Planning*](#), led by Edinburgh Living Lab in collaboration with the City of Edinburgh Council, applies AI-informed data analysis and co-design methods to guide neighbourhood planning and improve community decision-making processes. [*Smart Data Foundry*](#) on the other hand partners with local authorities for policymaking within the welfare & social services, and economy & finance segments.

Finally, 4 projects work directly with **frontline public service organisations** (L5), such as the [*Influence Policing*](#) research on targeted behavioural communication practices in police strategy teams, and the [*Digital and Artificial Intelligence Transformation Lab*](#), which collaborates with public agencies to support the practical adoption and evaluation of AI-driven service transformation.

3.2.2 Public Policy Areas

The largest share of activity (52 projects) relates to **Government Administration and Data Systems**, focusing on how data is collected, integrated, governed, and operationalised within public bodies. This includes work on digital government, administrative data pipelines, record linkage, decision-support systems, and organisational transformation. Because these infrastructures underpin other areas of public policy, projects in this category often intersect with additional domains: for example, [*the Digital and Artificial Intelligence Transformation Lab*](#) supports organisational transformation and the adoption of AI across public services, while [*Smart Data Foundry*](#) develops secure financial data environments that inform welfare provision, local authority planning, and economic and financial governance. The prevalence of this domain therefore reflects its cross-cutting and enabling role, rather than a discrete policy issue area.

Moving from this system-wide layer to more substantive policy domains, we observe distinct clusters of activity in specific areas. The strongest concentration lies in **Policing, Border Control, Internal Security and Migration** (15 activities). This includes decision environments in policy and policing ([*Neuropolitics Research Lab– Migration Narratives*](#)), algorithmic communication and behavioural targeting in police practice ([*Influence Policing*](#)), and legal and ethical dimensions of algorithmic policing, with attention to transparency, human oversight, and rights-based safeguards ([*SCRIPT Centre*](#)).

In the **Justice and Legal System**, (12 activities), research addresses the evidential and procedural implications of AI in legal contexts, including governance, accountability, and the interpretation of automated decision systems. This includes work in the [*SCRIPT Centre*](#), which examines legal and regulatory frameworks for emerging technologies, and collaborative work between Law and Informatics which advances technical methods for assessing how language models represent legal categories and argumentation, contributing to debates on the reliability of AI-supported legal reasoning and evidence handling.

In **Climate, Energy and Environment** (10 activities), research focuses on environmental modelling, sustainability planning, and impact assessment. Examples include the [*Edinburgh Earth Initiative*](#), [*AI for Digital Twin Earth*](#) collaboration and the [*AI for Net Zero*](#) project, which use machine learning to support climate policy modelling and infrastructure planning.

Research in **Welfare and Social Services** (9 activities) applies administrative and observational data to understand and address social inequalities. This includes the [*Perceptions of Edinburgh*](#) project, which examines neighbourhood characteristics linked to health resilience, [*Smart Data Foundry*](#) and [*SCADR*](#).

In **Media and Public Information** (at least 7 activities), research focuses on algorithmic transparency, editorial accountability and responsible AI use in news and information systems. This includes collaboration with the BBC to co-design value-aligned newsroom practices and strengthen journalists' understanding of algorithmic systems ([*Making AI Intelligible for Public Service Journalism*](#)), and work examining the ethical and technical dimensions of AI in international news production ([*BRAID: Responsible AI in International Public Service Media*](#)) conducted in partnership with the Public Media Alliance.

Finally, our desk-based research revealed comparatively less research activity in **Economic and Financial Governance, Foreign and Development Policy, Military and Defence** and **Emergency Services** domains. However, we note some important projects addressing these domains, such as [*PeaceRep's PeaceTech*](#).

3.3 Cross-cutting Insights

The network analysis shows that collaboration and expertise within the University's AI & Government landscape are anchored in three key Schools: Edinburgh Futures Institute (EFI), the School of Social and Political Science (SPS), and the School of Law. These units are the most connected and influential within the broader network, reflecting their central role in linking research on governance, ethics, and public policy. Below, we provide visual representations of the person-level and school-level networks. Please note that the spatial arrangement in the network visualisations reflects relational proximity. Nodes are positioned nearer if they share more connections. Spatial distance itself is not interpretable; the layout is illustrative rather than quantitative.

Figure 1. Network structure of past and present AI & Government research at the individual level

Figure 2. Network structure of past and present AI & Government research at the school level

Beyond the institutional structure of collaboration, we also observe clear patterns in the substantive focus of research activity. Work on the Governance of AI and AI in Policymaking appears across a wide range of policy areas and institutional levels, indicating that these categories operate as cross-cutting points of coordination within the public sector. In contrast, administrative and organisational applications are more common in operational and service-delivery contexts, while participatory and consultative uses remain comparatively limited. The heatmaps illustrate these patterns, showing how forms of AI-related research are positioned across policy domains (Figure 3) and levels of government (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Heatmap of Research Activities by AI Use and Public Policy Areas

Figure 4. Heatmap of Research Activities by AI Use and Levels of Government

4. Overview of Existing AI & Government Teaching Activities

We identified 32 courses and two doctoral degree programmes across the University that engage with themes related to Artificial Intelligence and its application in government and public policy. These courses span both undergraduate and postgraduate levels, with the majority offered within the EFI and the SPS.

Undergraduate teaching tends to focus on the societal and political implications of AI, offering students foundational understanding of how automation, data, and algorithmic systems shape governance and decision-making. Postgraduate courses, by contrast, often adopt a more interdisciplinary and applied perspective—integrating ethical, technical, and policy dimensions of AI. EFI in particular offers a large share of postgraduate provision, reflecting its cross-college role in developing programmes that connect data science and public policy. Overall, the current teaching portfolio demonstrates a strong institutional capacity in AI ethics, governance, and public sector innovation. We provide the list of courses in Appendix A, Table A1.

5. Overview of Existing AI & Government Exec-Ed Activities

The University's executive education activity in AI includes at least four dedicated programmes delivered across the Business School, Informatics, EFI, and the Law School. These programmes are designed for senior leaders, policy teams, and specialist practitioners, and combine technical, organisational, and legal perspectives. AI and Generative AI for Leaders, for example, provides a six-week introduction to core machine-learning concepts, generative AI capabilities, ethics, and regulatory considerations, while Future of Marketing: Digital Marketing, AI and Data examines how AI reshapes decision-making and communication within organisations.

Alongside these open programmes, cross-School collaboration enables tailored provision for specific partners. Recent examples include a bespoke 1.5-day course on AI for Senior Managers in Financial Services, delivered in partnership with Pinsent Masons, and a four-day programme on AI and Data Ethics developed for NatWest Group's leadership teams. This combination of interdisciplinary teaching and flexible delivery is establishing a strong foundation for future executive training in responsible and strategic adoption of AI. Appendix B, Table B1 includes links to each exec-ed programme identified through our search.

6. Discussion and Strategic Implications

The mapping shows that the University has a strong and visible concentration of expertise in responsible and accountable AI for public-sector contexts, particularly in the Governance of AI and the use of AI in Policymaking. These areas appear not only as the most active in terms of the number of projects, but also as the most cross-cutting, spanning multiple policy domains and levels of government, as illustrated in the heatmaps in Section 3.3. This reinforces the view that governance and strategic policymaking functions are not isolated specialisms but represent system-level strengths that connect work across EFI, SPS, Law and Informatics. These strengths are further supported by established partnerships with government agencies, regulators, and public-sector organisations. Taken together, they provide a clear foundation for developing a more coherent institutional profile around AI & Government—one that draws together existing work, supports shared teaching and professional training pathways, and strengthens engagement with external partners.

7. Emerging Priorities and Future Directions

The workshop held following the preparation of this interim report provided an opportunity to gain feedback on the initial mapping and to discuss where colleagues see the most pressing needs and opportunities for the University's work on AI & Government. The discussion affirmed the strengths and

the patterns of research activities within UoE identified through the desk-based exercise, while also drawing attention to a set of cross-cutting priorities that should shape the next phase of the initiative. In what follows, we summarise the domain-specific reflections and outline the core priorities for future development that emerged from these discussions.

7.1 Domain-Specific Reflections

In addition to these cross-cutting priorities, the workshop surfaced a range of domain-specific reflections linked to the four areas of AI use identified in the earlier mapping. Below we outline these:

Governance of AI: Reflections on the governance of AI centred on questions of oversight, sovereignty, and the political economy of critical infrastructures. Colleagues highlighted the increasingly complex assemblages of private supply chains, international dependencies, and distributed systems that shape how AI technologies are produced, deployed, and governed. Issues of trust, responsibility, privacy, and accountability were viewed as central, particularly given the rapid pace of technological change and the lack of stabilised definitions or regulatory frameworks. Discussions also emphasised the sociotechnical nature of AI infrastructures, noting that technologies, organisational practices, and communities interact in ways that can be unpredictable and that governance must account for these dynamics. Edinburgh's strengths in law, social science, informatics, engineering, and design uniquely position the University to lead work on infrastructure governance, AI sovereignty, and the development of responsible, human-centred oversight frameworks.

AI in Policymaking: Reflections in this area underscored the difficulty of applying AI meaningfully when policy problems, desired outcomes, and available data are often fragmented or poorly aligned. Colleagues noted that inconsistently collected or weakly documented data can undermine analytical efforts and lead to misplaced confidence in technical tools. A recurring theme was the need to distinguish policymaking from decision-making and to recognise that evidence generated through AI is only one element within broader institutional, political, and organisational dynamics. There is significant opportunity to draw on Edinburgh's strengths in policy, politics, informatics, and behavioural research to examine how knowledge systems, actors, and ideas evolve over time, and to understand where AI can and cannot contribute across the policy cycle—from issue definition to evaluation. These reflections highlight the value of interdisciplinary approaches that connect technical capability with the realities of policymaking.

AI in Participatory and Consultative Processes: In this domain, colleagues noted both the opportunities and risks associated with using AI to support democratic engagement. AI can amplify underrepresented voices, help synthesise large volumes of qualitative input, and support more responsive consultation processes, yet it also raises questions of legitimacy, transparency, and due process. Concerns included the potential for feedback loops, model subversion, and representational distortions—particularly when minority voices are amplified or obscured in ways that alter the perceived distribution of public opinion.

There was strong interest in exploring how co-design, participatory methods, and experimental approaches might help shape more inclusive and accountable practices. With Scotland being one of the world's leading ecosystems for democratic innovation, there is significant potential for interdisciplinary work within the University of Edinburgh that links AI tools to the evolving needs of participatory governance.

AI in Administrative and Organisational Processes: Discussions in this domain highlighted the challenge of moving from scattered pilot projects to infrastructures that are scalable, sustainable, and fit for organisational use. Questions of where data is stored, who controls compute resources, and how different systems interoperate were seen as central barriers to effective adoption. Colleagues also pointed to limited internal capacity within public bodies, including under-resourced IT teams and a lack of clear strategies for reskilling and long-term maintenance. The tension between outsourcing to large private-sector providers and developing in-house capability emerged as a recurring concern, particularly given dependencies on non-UK vendors. Edinburgh's expertise in systems design, data infrastructure, and large-scale compute positions the University to support efforts to build workable, end-use-oriented solutions and to inform debates about the organisational choices involved in scaling public-sector AI.

7.2 Cross-Cutting Priorities and Strategic Directions

Strengthening Internal Visibility, Coordination, and Collaborative Capacity: The need for clearer visibility and coordination across existing activity emerged as a central priority. Much of the University's work on AI in public-sector contexts is extensive but dispersed, and new colleagues in particular face difficulties identifying overlapping expertise. Developing simple mechanisms that make ongoing work easier to locate—such as shared points of contact, curated overviews, or lightweight mapping tools—would improve awareness across Schools. Specifically, Regular spaces for coming together such as workshops, roundtables, or informal discussion settings would play an important role in enabling exchange and building connections across otherwise dispersed work. Strengthening visibility and connectivity in this way would provide the foundation for a more connected research landscape and support a more coherent internal institutional profile.

There is also the need for structures that enable sustained collaboration once connections are made. Many challenges associated with public-sector AI span technical, organisational, political, and legal domains, requiring approaches that move beyond disciplinary boundaries. While the University already holds considerable expertise across these areas, there is scope to develop shared research agendas, joint methodological approaches, and closer partnerships with public bodies. By bringing related expertise into closer alignment, such groupings would also help enable competitive external funding bids. Enhancing this collaborative capacity would help consolidate Edinburgh's strengths and deepen its contribution to debates on AI in government.

Leveraging External Funding, Partnerships, and Institutional Delivery Capacity: A second priority concerns strengthening the University’s capacity to mobilise external resources around its AI & Government activity. While the mapping revealed substantial engagement with government bodies, regulators, and public-sector organisations, there is scope to better align research, consultancy, and executive education activities around shared themes and capabilities, enabling more coordinated engagement with funders and partners. Developing clearer mechanisms of external engagement would support the development of competitive research bids, consultancy projects, and executive education provision, and help convert existing expertise into sustained partnerships. In this way, externally funded and commissioned activity can be better supported by—and feed back into—the University’s broader AI & Government research and training ecosystem.

National Capability and the Scaling of AI in the Public Sector: The workshop also drew attention to questions of national capability, particularly the challenge of scaling AI systems from small pilots to sustainable national infrastructures. Issues of procurement, long-term stewardship, and dependency on multinational providers shape the extent to which public bodies can build and maintain trustworthy systems. Edinburgh’s technical assets—including advanced computing infrastructure and expertise in system-level design—place the University in a strong position not only to contribute to debates on how public-sector AI can be developed, scaled, and governed, but also to act as a focal point for collaboration with government partners.

At the same time, it is important to note that many colleagues engage with policymakers through advisory, convening, and agenda-setting activities that may not always result in formal research outputs and were therefore not fully captured in the present mapping. These forms of engagement play a critical role in shaping policy debates and building trust with government actors. In thinking about future structures and support mechanisms, there is scope to better recognise and integrate these individuals as connectors whose contributions are central to how the University interacts with government.

By bringing together technical expertise, research-led insight, and established policy-facing engagement, the University can strengthen its position as a leading centre of innovation in public-sector AI and a first port of call for government bodies seeking research, advisory, and training support on system design, governance, and national resilience.

8. Methodology

The mapping exercise was carried out in three parallel streams:

1. **Research activities**—identifying projects, centres, and publications related to AI in government or public policy.

2. **Teaching activities**—identifying courses, programmes, and training modules with relevance to AI and the public sector.
3. **Executive education activities**—identifying executive education programmes, professional development courses, and training activities with relevance to AI and the public sector.

Each stream used a combination of desk research and targeted searches, but the specific data sources and mapping approaches differed. Below we outline these procedures.

8.1 Data Collection

For research activities, data collection combined desk research, keyword-based searches, and a snowballing approach. We began with an initial brainstorming exercise to identify colleagues already known to be working on AI-related topics with potential relevance to government or the public sector. This list served as a starting point for a snowballing process:

- We reviewed PURE profiles (via Research Explorer) and University webpages of the initially identified colleagues to record their relevant projects, publications, and initiatives.
- When projects involved multiple collaborators, all associated researchers were added, progressively expanding the network.
- We conducted keyword searches in Research Explorer using terms such as “artificial intelligence”, “AI”, and “machine learning”, manually reviewing project descriptions to identify those linked to public policy or public sector applications.
- To enrich the dataset, we also searched a publicly available database of successful UKRI grant applications, identifying University of Edinburgh researchers engaged in externally funded AI–government projects.

Each identified person was recorded along with their associated *activities*, defined broadly to include research projects, centres, hubs, initiatives, or publications demonstrating engagement with AI use, governance, or policy implications.

For teaching activities, we primarily used the *Degree Regulations and Programmes of Study* (DRPS) website. Using its Google-powered search function, we searched for terms such as “Artificial Intelligence” and “Artificial Intelligence and Public Policy”. Each suggested result was reviewed manually, with judgements made based on course titles and descriptions to determine relevance to AI and the public sector. For each identified course, we recorded the course convenor, School, and level (undergraduate or postgraduate).

To complement this desk-based search, we also consulted key staff members across relevant Schools to identify additional courses that may not have been captured through the DRPS search. These inputs helped to expand and validate the teaching activities dataset.

For executive education activities, we reviewed executive education offerings across relevant Schools, Centres, and Institutes, including the Business School, Edinburgh Futures Institute, Informatics, and the School of Law. Programme descriptions, case studies, and executive education webpages were examined to identify activities addressing AI, data, digital transformation, governance, ethics, or public-sector applications. Both open-enrolment programmes and bespoke courses delivered for external organisations were included.

8.2 Typology Development

To organise and interpret the mapped activities, we developed a two-dimensional typology that captures 1) the forms of AI use in the public sector and 2) the areas of government or public policy in which these uses relate. We developed these typologies iteratively. While the initial framework was based on early team discussions, the review of projects and activities led to the addition of new categories where relevant work did not fit existing ones. In some cases, activities intersected more than one area, so multiple coding was applied to capture their breadth. The two dimensions are summarised below:

AI Use Types

1. **AI in Administration and organisational processes:** applications of AI in internal systems such as HR, finance, or management tools.
2. **AI in Policymaking:** uses of AI in designing, implementing, or evaluating policy and strategy.
3. **AI in Participatory or consultative processes:** applications supporting citizen input, deliberation, or public consultation.
4. **Governance of AI:** research and activity related to regulation, accountability, ethics, and democratic oversight of AI.

Government & Public Sector Domains

To capture where research engages the public sector, we distinguish between (1) the level of government (L) involved and (2) the specific policy area (PA) addressed.

<i>Levels of Government</i>	L1. International / Transnational L2. National (UK Central Government & Executive Agencies) L3. Scottish Government and other devolved administrations L4. Local & Regional Government (councils, regional agencies) L5. Public Service Organisations / Frontline Delivery Bodies
<i>Policy Areas:</i>	PA1. Foreign & Development Policy PA2. Military, Defense & National Security PA3. Economy & Financial Governance PA4. Public Administration & Data PA5. Media & Public Information PA6. Climate, Energy & Environment PA7. Policing, Border Control, Internal Security and Migration PA8. Justice & Legal System PA9. Emergency Services PA10. Welfare & Social Services

8.3 Mapping Approach

Each mapped activity was reviewed qualitatively to determine its relevance to one or more AI use types and policy domains defined in the typology. This process involved reading project summaries, publication abstracts, and grant descriptions, as well as visiting project or centre websites to understand their focus and scope. When the information available online was insufficient, we directly contacted project leads or collaborators to clarify the nature and policy relevance of their work.

Activities were then coded manually according to the typology. Where projects spanned multiple categories—such as combining policymaking and governance aspects, or engaging with several policy domains—they were assigned to all relevant categories. This ensured that the analysis captured both the depth and overlap of AI-related work across the University. The coded dataset was used to produce summary statistics showing the distribution of activity across AI use types and policy domains.

We also conducted a network analysis linking researchers, research activities, and areas of AI use to examine how expertise and collaboration are structured within the University’s AI & Government research landscape. In the network, nodes represent people, schools, research activities, or AI use types, while edges capture two kinds of relationships: (1) a person’s or school’s involvement in a research activity, and (2) a research activity’s connection to a particular form of AI use.

Separate network visualisations were produced at the individual and school levels to map how collaboration and AI expertise are distributed across the institution. To identify the most connected and influential nodes within the network, we calculated standard centrality measures—degree, betweenness,

and eigenvector centrality—which capture how extensively a node is linked, how strongly it bridges different parts of the network, and how closely it is connected to other highly linked nodes. These measures were used to highlight key points of convergence in AI-related research and collaboration across the University.

We also examined how research activities are distributed across different areas of public policy and levels of government. To do this, we leveraged from heatmaps to demonstrate how these forms of AI-related research span policy areas and government levels, highlighting where activity is concentrated and where it is more limited.

Appendix A. Teaching Activities Related to AI & Government

School	Course / Degree Programme Name	Level
Business School	HR/People Analytics	postgraduate
Edinburgh Medical School	AI for Care in the Digital Age	postgraduate
EFI	Algorithmic Bias, Fairness and Justice	postgraduate
EFI	Data and Artificial Intelligence Ethics, Law and Governance	postgraduate
EFI	Data and Artificial Intelligence Ethics as a Practice	postgraduate
EFI	Democracy, Rights and the Rule of Law in the Data-Driven Society	postgraduate
EFI	Digital Influence	postgraduate
EFI	Environmental Sustainability and Artificial Intelligence	postgraduate
EFI	Future Governance	postgraduate
EFI	Text Mining for Social Researchers	postgraduate
EFI	The Neuropolitics of Decision Making	postgraduate
EFI	Transport and Society	postgraduate

Engineering	Sensing, Processing and AI for Defence and Security	degree programme
Informatics	Designing Responsible NLP	degree programme
Informatics	Researching Responsible and Trustworthy Natural Language Processing	postgraduate
Informatics	Understanding Society with Big Data: Computational Social Science	undergraduate
Law	Advanced Legal Reasoning	undergraduate
Law	Fundamentals of EU Competition Law	postgraduate
Law	International Human Rights in the Digital Era	undergraduate
Law	Legal Technology in the Justice System	postgraduate
Law	Regulation of Autonomous systems	postgraduate
Law	Robotics and the Law	undergraduate
Law	Robotics, AI and the Law	postgraduate
PPLS	Algorithmic Bias	undergraduate
PPLS	Ethics of Artificial Intelligence	undergraduate
SPS	Advanced Topics in Global Security	undergraduate
SPS	AI, Digital Technology and Politics	undergraduate
SPS	Controversies in the Data Society	postgraduate
SPS	Data and Society	postgraduate
SPS	Digital Media and Democracy	undergraduate
SPS	Foundations in Responsible Research and Innovation	postgraduate
SPS	Governance, Development and Poverty in Africa	postgraduate
SPS	International Regulation and Governance	postgraduate
SPS	Neuropolitics	undergraduate

Table A1: Courses and Degree Programmes on AI & Government across Schools

Appendix B. Exec-Ed Activities Related to AI & Government

School	Course / Degree Programme Name	Duration	Link
Business School, Informatics, EFI, Law	AI and Generative AI for Leaders: Empowering Digital Transformation and Strategic Decision Making	6 weeks	https://www.business-school.ed.ac.uk/executive-education/ai-and-generative-ai-for-leaders
Business School, EFI (for Pinsent Masons Law Firm)	AI for Senior Managers in Financial Services	1.5 days	https://www.business-school.ed.ac.uk/executive-education/ai-for-senior-managers-in-financial-services
Business School	Future of Marketing: Digital Marketing, AI and Data	6 weeks	https://www.business-school.ed.ac.uk/executive-education/future-of-marketing
Business School (NatWest Group)	AI and Data Ethics	4 days	https://www.business-school.ed.ac.uk/executive-education/case-studies/ai-data-ethics-programme

			natwest-group-leaders-colleagues
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Table A1: Executive Education Programmes on AI & Government across Schools